

The loss and generation of groundwater NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} of tropical peatland

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ABSTRACT

*The existence of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} in groundwater of tropical peatland determines the quality of peatland and potentially affects the surrounding ecosystems. This research aimed to determine the loss and generation of groundwater NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} of inland peat in West Kalimantan, and the factors affecting those processes. Three research plots were located in oil palm (*Elaeisguineensis* Jacq.) plantation (OP) while one plot was established in a secondary forest (SF). Water samplings were conducted fortnightly from 50 and 200 cm depths with three replications for each plot. Environmental factors monitored included daily rainfall and weekly groundwater level. This research showed that NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} generation occurred in the presence of oxygen. The higher concentration of NO_3^- in OP than in SF was attributed to a more oxidized(aerobic) condition in OP than in SF. The lowering of groundwater level during the dry season in October 2015 increased the formation of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} . In the wet season, the loss of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were affected by movement of groundwater both laterally and vertically. The loss dramatically increased when the drained peat was washed by the high intensity rainfall. The rise of groundwater level increased peat moisture and subsequently increased nitrification and SO_4^{2-} generation. NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} found in the anaerobic layer were derived from those generations in aerobic layer.*

Keywords: NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , groundwater, oil palm plantation, tropical peatland

INTODUCTION

Peatland is less favorable for crop due to low nutrient content, low pH, low bulk density, low bearing capacity, and high water table level (Agus and Subikse, 2008; Haraguchi et al., 2000; Driessen, 1978). However, due to the limited productive land of mineral soils, peatlands are considered potential areas for agricultural crops including oil palm plantation.

Peatlands conversion to agricultural fields mostly followed by drainage activity which causes water loss from upper peat layer and creates anaerobic layer, leading to accelerated peat decomposition rates. The high peat decomposition and low water table level characterize drained tropical peatlands. In the upper layer of soil solution of peatlands, where the contact

between water and oxygen take place, the oxidative reactions occur such as nitrification and generation of sulfate acid (van Breemen et al., 1983; Abrams et al., 2016; Mettrop et al., 2015; Mettrop et al., 2014). In the submerged condition, the soil solution experiences the reduction reactions such as denitrification and sulfate reduction (van Breemen et al., 1983; Mettrop et al., 2015; Mettrop et al., 2014). This research was aimed to investigate the change of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} concentration in the soil solution, in the perspective for their loss and generation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field study was conducted in the inland peat in Ketapang District, West Kalimantan Province, Indonesia, which had 2,800 mm of annual rainfall. Oil palm plantation in this study sites was established since year 2002 (16 years old during this research in 2016), while secondary forests remain exist in a small area in the same dome, with the distance of 4km between OP and SF. We established three oil palm plots (OP1, OP2, and OP3) and one control plot of secondary forest (SF). For every plots, we installed polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pipes with a diameter of 10 cm, used for soil solution sampling. The pipes were installed to reach 50 and 200 cm depths of peat, which located between trees, and remained 50 cm was above the peat surface. Soil solution samples were collected fortnightly from the pipes by a hose. The concentrations of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were measured using a high-performance liquid chromatograph. Water table depth was measured using 10 cm diameter and 150 cm long perforated PVC pipe, which installed in the middle of each plot. During this study, the type, schedule, application way, and the average rate of fertilizer application in each plots were monitored.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Peat environmental factors

El Niño was experienced from September to October 2015, where rainfall was very low and an extreme drought occurred (Field et al., 2016; Parker et al., 2016). During El Niño, the water table lowered below 150 cm and immeasurable due to the limited pipe length (Fig. 1). Wet season started at the end of October 2015, where the accumulation of rainfall started to calculated. During the wet season, water table levels in the OP plots rose and were maintained by water gates at 30–50 cm in West Kalimantan. The floor of SF plot had been submerged since the end of April 2016 because the absence of drainage channel.

Figure 1. Daily cumulative rainfall (mm) from September 2015 to October 2016 (line) and the depth of the water table (circle). El Niño occurred during September–October 2015.

Anion concentration at different depths

Anion concentrations of soil solutions from oil palm plantation plots are shown in Fig. 2. The oxidizing condition at 50 cm depths was reflected in the soil solution composition. Concentration of NO_3^- at 50 cm depth were significantly higher than at 200 cm depth. The generation of NO_3^- may have been caused by oxidation process of peat in the upper layer. The soil solution from the upper layer of the 50 cm depth had more contact with the ambient environment, including atmospheric oxygen, than the deep 200 cm layer, resulting in oxidative reactions (Fenner and Freeman 2011; Bougon et al. 2011; Adamson et al. 2001; van Bremen et al. 1983). Different pattern was found for SO_4^{2-} where SO_4^{2-} at 50 cm depth was significantly lower than at 200 cm depth, reflecting the contribution of marine deposit in bottom mineral layer.

Figure 2. Means NO_3^- (left) and SO_4^{2-} (right) concentration of soil solution in OP. Error bar indicates standard deviation. The different character indicates significant difference between 50 and 200 cm depth using t-test.

Anion concentration at different land uses

Anion concentrations of soil solutions from different land uses are shown in **Fig. 3**. NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} concentration in OP were significantly higher than of in SF at 50 cm depth. NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were generated more in OP, which experienced drained condition and inorganic fertilizer application. Drained peatland exposes peat to aerobic condition while inorganic fertilizer application triggers microbial decomposer activity, which both would accelerates peat decomposition. At 200 cm depth, only NO_3^- concentration in OP was significantly higher than of in SF. The influence of marine deposit in bottom mineral layer of OP caused the higher concentration of SO_4^{2-} in 200 cm depth compare to SF.

Figure 3. Means NO_3^- (left) and SO_4^{2-} (right) concentrations of soil solution between oil palm plantation (OP) and secondary forest (SF). Error bar indicates standard deviation. The same character indicates no significant difference between OP and SF using t-test.

The temporal loss and generation of anions

In the drought, which occurred in October 2015, the concentrations of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} at 50 cm were higher than at 200 cm depths. Drought induced oxidative reactions at an aerobic layer of 50 cm, resulting the generation of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} (Cussel et al. 2013; Bougon et al. 2011; Loeb et al. 2008; Eimers et al. 2007; Adamson et al. 2001; van Bremen et al. 1983). Organic N and S were oxidized to NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} , respectively.

The loss of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} occurred through reduction reactions in the 200 cm of an anaerobic layer, such as denitrification and sulfate reduction (Cussel et al. 2015; Adamson et al. 2001; van Bremen et al. 1983). Low concentrations of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} during the drought may have also been because of these reactions (Fig. 4).

A sharp drop of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} concentrations in 50 and 200 cm layers occurred at the commencement of wet season in November 2015, possibly caused by rewetting event which include several processes of dilution, transportation, and flowage. The anions may be transported from 50 and 200 cm layers to the lower layers. These low anions concentration of 0.7-1.3 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ persisted for three months from November 2015 to January 2016. Furthermore, the low concentration of these anions in the deeper layer indicated the continuation of denitrification and sulfate reduction processes.

The generation of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were occurred in early March 2016, which likely because of the enhanced microbial activity caused by the increased moisture content (Fig. 1). The reduced rainfall intensity also supported these increases. At that time, the increase NO_3^- at 200 cm depth derives from oxidative layer, while the sharp increase of the generation of SO_4^{2-} at both 50 and 200 cm depth indicates the contribution of bottom mineral layer.

Figure 4. Fluctuations of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} concentrations in the soil solution. Arrows show sharp decreases in soil solution concentrations.

CONCLUSIONS

The loss and generation of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} in soil solutions of tropical peatlands was investigated. The factors affecting the loss of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were high intensity of rewetting on dried peatland, which occurred at 50 and 200 cm depth. The loss of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were also caused by reductive environment in 200 cm depth. Moreover, the generation of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} occurred in the dry period, where oxygen easily penetrates to 50 cm depth. The existing of marine sediment in bottom mineral layer contributes to the high generation of SO_4^{2-} . Land use types influences NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} generation, where the exposed and the fertilized peat of OP accelerates peat decomposition and generates NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} much higher than nature peat of SF.

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